

Title: Change in blood donation patterns – analysis of data from a large German hospital between 2010-2017

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Objectives

To understand changes over time, we describe blood donation patterns in a large German hospital. We do so to help decision-makers in hospitals and health policy makers to understand pertaining changes, to design donor engagement strategies and to more effectively manage blood supply.

Methods

A retrospective analysis of administrative data from Universitätsklinikum Hamburg-Eppendorf (UKE), a hospital with 1,460 beds and a substantial share in the blood donation market in Hamburg (1.8 million inhabitants) was conducted using data from donors over the period 2010-2017. The analysis focussed on whole blood donations which included both successful and unsuccessful donations and how they changed over time.

Results

Preliminary results show a total of 225,807 donation attempts were made between 2010 and 2017, with 18,863 (8.40%) unsuccessful donations. Unsuccessful donations can be explained by the donor not meeting the entry criteria or the donation being stopped due to medical reasons. Donations peaked in 2014 with 30,382 donations compared with 26,309 in 2017 and 26,950 in 2010. The average age of the donors increased over the time period from 40.6 years in 2010 to 42.7 in 2017. 60.4% of donations were donated by male donors, which remained relatively constant over the time period. Most donations were made on a Tuesday (26.3%) with the second most popular day being Wednesday (23.9%). The popularity of these days may be explained by later opening hours. Donations at weekends were not possible with the exception of special events. Most donations (93.3%) were made by repeat donors who have donated more than one time. Donations by first-time donors have increased over the time period from 1085 donations (4.0%) in 2010 to 2022 (7.7%) in 2017.

Discussion

Understanding blood donation patterns will help to ensure an efficient management of hospital blood supply. Preliminary results suggest that strategies to maintain repeat donors are more important than generating new donors as they account for the majority of donations. There is also a potentially large opportunity cost of failing to convert new donors into repeat donors given that first-time donations are of very limited use until further testing is performed in subsequent donations.